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Psychological Determinants of Digital Pedagogical Competence of a Defectologist

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Abstract

A modern man lives and development takes place within the received information incentives that build character and behavior through responses to these incentives. And information contacts are the main way of interaction between people. It is a simplified form of communication, which exclude deep meaning and content from persons' communication. Any information contact – it's just "here and now", and communication is all over the place available to people who have successfully adapted to the conditions of the information and economic society and managed to maintain the integrity of the "self". The essence of the continuity of this approach is the recognition of the primacy of the internal environment of a person, which is understood as his psychological content, over the external environment, which is understood as the social reality of modern society. . The author's attitude to the described problem is offered. Using the theoretical and methodological framework of Russian psychology, the author points to the need to pay attention to the following psychological aspects: firstly, as a direction indicator of the level of innovation in professional activities, secondly, as to the causes of internal mechanisms of this movement, thirdly, as a guarantee of innovation performance in professional activities (Balymova, 2008; Klimov, 2007; Ushakov, 2006). The results of this investigation are to assess the real possibilities and prospects of development of the society in the context of its constant requests for innovation. It is noted that at the present moment professional characteristics, different interpretations of digital behavior and the importance of internal human resources in all sectors of society are well-known, but there is still no any logical linkage between these components, the components that determine the efficiency in the aggregate required changes to social progress.

Keywords: digital pedagogical competence, digital behavior, psychological determinants, defectologist.

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Introduction

The choice of digital pedagogical competence of a defectologist as a positive factor in solving the problem of improving the quality of education is due to the fact that at present the world in general and our country in particular have entered into the information epoch, which means the rapid development of the society – the totality of activities, relationships, social and mass consciousness characteristic for this stage acquire new qualities. Now in the modern world the security problems are relevant both for Russia and for the world community. Nowadays living conditions imply a wide range of threats and dangers not only of natural but of social origin, determined, in particular, by the psychological characteristics of society itself. In such conditions, there is a strong need for psychological resources that ensure the security of the individual. Such a resource could be the ability to maintain, to control the integrity of one's own personality, to develop oneself and maintain one's social environment.

The subject of this part of the paper is the psychological characteristics of defectologists who agreed or aimed to increase the level of their digital pedagogical competence.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Purpose of the study. The paper shows that there is a definite correlation between psychological characteristics and implementation of digital behavior in professional activities.

Literature review

The research hypothesis was the assumption that the nature of the decision-making process to increase the level of digital pedagogical competence is determined by the degree of severity and the nature of the relationship of psychological characteristics of a personality of a defectologist.

Currently, all over the world are actively engaged in solving problems related to the peculiarities of the development of professional defectology, in particular, concerning the sphere of inclusive education:

- the area of inclusive education, as a zone of increased responsibility on the part of the state, public structures, schools and parents of children with special needs, when a child with disabilities is faced with an inaccessible environment, untrained teachers, and unprofessional teaching assistants (tutors) (Perry, 2017)

- on the way of inclusion of proposed development professionals for the enrichment of the quality inclusive education (Florian, 2014)

examination of existing models of teaching effectiveness, given the role of teaching assistants in classrooms and the role of teachers managing teaching assistants to improve the quality of support for children with disabilities and enhance professionalism in working with them specialists (Abulhanova-Slavskaya, 1999; Vygotskii, 1995; Derkach, 2003; Krotova, 2014)

"Special education in Russia and abroad" (Malofeev, 2009), the main specificity of the transition period of the defectological direction is a change in the attitude to people with disabilities, when it is necessary to understand what are the real resources to achieve an "accessible environment" and what needs to be done in conditions of resource scarcity.

Methodology

Organization and stages of research. Analysis of the results of an empirical study of digital pedagogical competence as a psychological and pedagogical condition for improving the quality of the educational environment.

Statistical comparison of indicators by t-student test for independent groups was made at the first stage of the research and it gave us the following results.

Groups 1 and 2 (these are the groups of defectologists studied) differ in the severity of the following indicators ($p = 0.05$):

- No. 7 "the pedantic type" (more indicated in the second group than in the first group);
- No. 8 "the excitable type" (more indicated in the first group than in the second group).

Thus, the testees of the first group are more impulsive than the testees of the second group, and they weakly control their desires and motives, spontaneous in their feelings manifestation, while the testees of the second group, in comparison with the first group, are characterized by increased rigidity, inertness of mental processes, the idea of order and accuracy becomes their life meaning model.

Results

The results of divergent empirical data analysis are presented further. There were found the significant differences in the correlation between the following indicators:

- the correlation between indicators No. 1 "the focus on self" and No. 14 "the cyclothymic type of personality accentuation" – in group 1, it is a direct correlation ($p < 0.05$); in group 2, it is a reverse correlation ($p = 0.01$). Thus, representatives of the second group are subject to frequent mood swings with less focus on themselves, and vice versa. And this trend is not observed for testees of the first group;

- the correlation between indicators No. 13 "the emotive types of personality accentuation" and No. 14 "the cyclothymic types of personality accentuation" – in group 1, it is a direct correlation ($p < 0.05$); in group 2, it is also a direct correlation ($p = 0.001$). That is, the testees of the second group are more impressionable and sensitive in the case of frequent mood and conditions changes, and vice versa. At the same time the respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence) of the first group are not characterized by this trend;

- the correlation between indicators No. 5 "the demonstrative type of personality accentuation" and No. 15 "the spontaneity of shopping behavior" – in group 1, there is a direct correlation ($p = 0.01$); in group 2, there is also a direct correlation ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the respondents of the first group are more demonstrative in social life situations, and vice versa. It is also possible that impulsive decisions are a way to demonstrate themselves and their capabilities. At the same time the respondents of the first group are not characterized by this trend.

The differences in the correlation between the following indicators are marked only at the trend level:

- the correlation between indicators No. 3 "the focus on team" and No. 8 "the excitable type of personality accentuation" – in group 1, there is a direct correlation ($p = 0.05$); in group 2 – a reverse correlation ($p < 0.05$). Thus, the desire to maintain social relationships under any circumstances is more determined by the tendency to increased impulsive activity among the respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence) of the first group, and vice versa. In the second group there is a tendency to the opposite;

- the correlation between indicators No. 4 "the search for thrills" and No. 7 "the pedantic type of personality accentuation" – in group 1, the correlation is reverse ($p < 0.05$); in group 2, it is direct ($p < 0.05$). That is, in the first group, the search for thrills will be more active in the case of low rigidity and pedantry, supported by the ideas of order and accuracy, and for the second group, the level of search for thrills will be determined by a high degree of pedantry, which indicates the conditionality of these two processes;

- the correlation between indicators No. 7 “the pedantic type of personality accentuation” and No. 9 “the hyperthymic type of personality accentuation” – in group 1, the correlation is reverse ($p < 0.05$), in group 2, it is direct ($p < 0.05$). Thus, in the first group, the testees’ positive excited mood, lack of discipline will be observed in the case of low rigidity and pedantry, and vice versa; and for the second group, the positive excited mood will be represented in the case of high rigidity and pedantry, that is, their subject to the ideas of accuracy.

Thereby, in the first group, there is a tendency to increase positive mood in case of committing spontaneous acts, and in the second group, there is a tendency to increase positive mood in case of committing deliberate actions.

Discussions

Analysis of the linear correlation values of the studied indicators. In the first group of testees, the following correlations were identified ($p = 0.01$):

- No. 1 “the focus on self” and No. 2 “the focus on business” – the correlation is reverse, that is, the testees of the first group with a significant focus on business, on doing the job as good as possible, focus on business cooperation are less aggressive in achieving status, dominance, less marked by irritability and anxiety;

- No. 5 “the demonstrative type” and No. 15 “the spontaneity” – the correlation is direct, that is, the respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence) of the first group are more demonstrative in the situation of making spontaneous purchases when shopping, and vice versa; it is also possible that the impulsive way of decisions making is a way of demonstrating oneself and one’s capabilities.

And in the first group of testees, the following correlations were identified as $p = 0.05$:

- No. 2 “the focus on business” and No. 3 “the focus on team” – the correlation is reverse, that is, in the first group, the focus on business cooperation is better if there is no dependence on the group and joint activities;

- No. 3 “the focus on team” and No. 8 “the excitable type” – the correlation is direct, that is, in this group, under any conditions the desire to maintain relationships with people and orientation to joint activity will be in the case of a tendency to increased impulsive reactivity in the field of attraction;

- No. 4 “the scale of the search for thrills” and No. 10 “the dysthymic type” – the correlation is direct, so for the first group the search for thrills and new experience occurs in the case of a pessimistic mood, and vice versa;

- No. 5 “the demonstrative type” and No. 7 “the pedantic type” – the correlation is reverse, that is, the demonstrative behavior of the testees of the first group will be manifested in the case of low rigidity and pedantry;

- No. 5 “the demonstrative type” and No. 13 “the emotive type” – the correlation is direct, thus, the first group testees demonstrative behavior will be manifested in case of high emotional sensitivity and possibly, as a result, in case of an abrupt mood change for an insignificant reason for others;

- No. 8 “the excitable type” and No. 12 “the affectively exalted type” – the correlation is direct, that is, in the case of a tendency to increased impulsive reactivity in the attraction sphere, there will be a tendency to affective exaltation, the same signs will be at the emotional level – everything comes from the temperament type;

- No. 12 “the affectively exalted type” and No. 15 “the spontaneity” – the correlation is reverse, that is, in the case of a tendency to affective exaltation, there will be less spontaneity in behavior, and vice versa.

In the second group of testees, the following correlations were identified ($p = 0.001$):

- No. 1 “the focus on self” and No. 2 “the focus on business” – the correlation is reverse, therefore, in this group of respondents, the more the person is interested in solving business problems and is focused on business cooperation, the less he has a focus on himself, that denotes less aggressiveness and rivalry in relations with colleagues;

- No. 13 “the emotive type” and No. 14 “the cyclothymic type” – a direct correlation – that is, in this group of respondents, people will be more sensitive and impressionable in the case of a high cyclical nature, frequent change of mood and conditions.

And in the second group of testees, the following correlations were identified as $p = 0.01$:

- No. 1 “the focus on self” and No. 13 “the emotive type” – the correlation is reverse, so the more impressionable and sensitive a person is, the less likely he / she will be oriented toward direct reward, aggressiveness in achieving status and a tendency to compete;

- No. 1 “the focus on self” and No. 14 “the cyclothymic type” – the correlation is reverse, that is, respondents will be prone to rivalry and aggressiveness in achieving status in case of a frequent change of mood;

- No. 2 “the focus on business” and No. 14 “the cyclothymic type” – a direct correlation, that is, in case of a frequent change of state and mood the testees will be oriented on business and interested in solving business problems, they will try to complete tasks as good as possible.

And the following correlations were identified as $p = 0.05$:

- No. 1 “the focus on self” and No. 3 “the focus on team” – the correlation is reverse, that is, under any circumstances the respondents tend to maintain relationships with people, oriented towards joint activities and social approval, less focused on themselves;

- No. 2 “the focus on business” and No. 3 “the focus on team” – the correlation is reverse, that is, in case of focus on communication and the desire to maintain relationships with people in any conditions the testees of this group are not interested in solving business issues and will not strive to complete tasks as good as possible;

- No. 2 “the focus on business” and No. 12 “the affectively exalted type” – a direct correlation, that is, the easier for respondents it is to move from a state of ecstasy to a state of sadness, the stronger the focus on business is and the more interest in solving business problems and propensity for business cooperation occur;

- 3 “the focus on team” and No. 15 “the spontaneity” – a direct correlation, so it can be assumed that the more the respondents are oriented towards social approval, the more a person manifests himself / herself, the more often he will make purchases when shopping under the influence of a momentary impulse.

Summarizing the results of the research, the testees of the first group are inclined to behave impulsively, under the influence of a momentary impulse, while the testees of the second group are reasonable at that kind of situations.

Conclusion

Analysis of statistical data of our empirical research revealed the following differences in the psychological characteristics of the two groups of respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence).

In the first group, the respondents are oriented toward the group rather than themselves, they are extroverted, sociable, do not show obvious aggression and rivalry in achieving certain statuses, and are tolerant to each other. It is also may be noticed that the members of the group do not show a penchant for business cooperation and focusing on solving business problems. In general, respondents are oriented towards relationships maintaining, they are ready to provide assistance and support, value emotional connections and relationships. The testees of the first group are characterized by impressionability, sensitivity, an easy transition between different-pole states (from sadness to joy); the respondents are impulsive, have little control over their drives and motives, are distinguished by an increased mood background, high activity, persistence of affective experiences. At the same time, in general, they are able to control the need for thrills, they are quite moderate in their satisfaction.

The respondents of the first group are impulsive and have little control over their desires and motives, spontaneous in their feelings manifestation; they are characterized by demonstrativeness in a situation of committing spontaneous acts.

The respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence) of the first group can be characterized by the statements: the desire to maintain relationships under any circumstances is more determined by the tendency to increased impulsive activity; and the search for thrills will be more active in case of low rigidity and pedantry (dominance of the ideas of order and accuracy) and at the same time there will be an increased positive mood.

Moreover, the testees of the first group have a significant focus on business – doing work as good as possible, they tend to business cooperation, are less aggressive in achieving status, authority, less characterized by irritability and anxiety.

In the second group, the respondents (defectologist willing to improve their digital competence) seek social approval in all situations of their lives, they are ready to help people, but not to the detriment of their own interests.

This group is characterized by an increased mood background, combined with optimism and high activity, but there is a tendency to frequent mood changes for a minor reason. Moreover, the testees are addicted to fears, fearfulness, especially impressionable and sensitive, they tend to have long passing through current conditions; they know how to control their needs for new experiences, moderate in satisfaction, reasonable at crucial moments of life.

The respondents of the second group are characterized by increased rigidity, inertness of mental processes; for them the idea of order and accuracy becomes the main meaning of their life, but at the same time there is a tendency to dependence of a frequent change of mood because of a self-orientation decrease – that is, if it is not possible for them to achieve their own goals, then, as a result, this leads to a decrease in control of the general mood background, and this, in turn, leads to an increase in impressionability and sensitivity.

Moreover, the second group of testees is characterized by a desire to maintain relationships under any circumstances, which reduces the level of their impulsive activity, while the level of search for thrills is determined by a high degree of pedantry. And they will have the increased positive mood in case of high rigidity and pedantry, if they endorse the ideas of accuracy.

In addition, in the second group of testees, the focus on self is manifested in pedantry, rigidity of behavior and increased positive mood – and in the presence of these factors it helps testees to reduce the cyclical nature of their mood and general level of their sensitivity and impulsivity.

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